

THE FEATURES OF MEDIA TEXTS IN THE TRANSLATION

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Abstract. *This article discusses the features of the English newspaper style. The results of the study of vocabulary, syntax and structure of an English newspaper article are given. As a research material, the author uses issues of The Guardian newspaper. It also describes how to correctly translate media texts using different language tools. We will mention about the usage of different styles of language in order to attract the readers' attention with help of cliches, epithets, puns and etc.*

Key words: *English newspaper style, media texts, language tools, cliches, epithets, puns*

ОСОБЕННОСТИ МЕДИАТЕКСТА В ПЕРЕВОДЕ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются особенности английского газетного стиля. Приведены результаты исследования лексики, синтаксиса и структуры англоязычной газетной статьи. В качестве материала исследования автор использует номера газеты The Guardian. Также описывается, как правильно переводить медиатексты с использованием различных языковых средств. Упомянем об использовании различных стилей языка для привлечения внимания читателей с помощью клише, эпитетов, каламбуров и т. д.*

Ключевые слова: *английский газетный стиль, медиатексты, языковые средства, клише, эпитеты, каламбуры.*

One of the important features of media texts of almost all genres is the combination of message and impact elements in them. Although the main function of mass communication is considered to be the transfer of information, this transfer is quite rarely completely neutral, that is, absolutely free from elements of influence on the audience. In most cases, the transfer of information is accompanied by a direct or veiled expression of evaluation, language means and speech techniques that encourage the audience to a certain reaction to the transmitted information, means of drawing attention to information or to the point of view expressed in the message.

A truly professional translator should be able to notice and adequately convey the ratio of the actual information and the expressive means of IT in his translation.

Among the actual linguistic and stylistic features of the language of the media, the totality of which distinguishes it from the language of other functional styles, one can name a high degree of standardization of the means used: a large percentage of stable and clichéd expressions, various journalistic clichés, lexicalized metaphors, standard terms and names, etc. (this feature is typical for news materials and reflects the desire of their authors to create an impression of absolute objectivity and impartiality). So, for informational messages in the media, such phrases as: *agenda; official visit; summit meeting; fruitful cooperation; bilateral agreement; peace negotiations, etc.* (Повестка дня; официальный визит; встреча на высшем уровне; плодотворное сотрудничество; двустороннее соглашение; мирные переговоры и т. п.)

Examples of the expressiveness of the language as a way of attracting the attention of the recipient, expressing attitudes towards the transmitted information, placing evaluative accents,

etc. can serve as speech clichés and clichés, evaluative epithets, direct appeals to the reader (these features most often characterize copyright, subscription materials). For example: *fortunately; unfortunately; unfortunately; bombshell effect; I note with bitterness; so-called; with connivance; you probably already guess what will be discussed, etc.* (к счастью; к несчастью; к сожалению; эффект разорвавшейся бомбы; с горечью замечу; так называемый; при попустительстве; вы, возможно уже догадываетесь, о чем пойдет речь и т. п.)

In recent years, the language of the media allows the use of colloquial, reduced, slang and even profanity, which is used to express a certain attitude (for example, ironic) of the author of the material, to create a certain image and stylistic (for example, humorous) effect, as well as to shock the audience and attracting a certain category of readers. For example: *“Since I sincerely don’t give a damn about politicians, I’ll talk about society”*; *“Well, what are you, a writer? Did you do something? etc.*

A special feature of media texts (and a special translation problem) are headlines built on puns, wordplays, quotations, allusions and deformed idioms. For example: *a string of bad luck; Creation of sushi (material about Japanese cuisine); When Queen Anne was alive. ; Who is to blame and what to do? etc.* («Оскар» невезения; Сотворение суши (материал о японской кухне); При царе Горохе; Кто виноват и что делать? и т. п.) It is obvious that such headings, like many other expressive elements, cannot be translated literally. The translation “response” to a pun in the source text should ideally be a meaningful pun in the translated text. If a solution to such a problem cannot be found (which happens quite often), it is better to change the title completely, making it neutral, but clear in meaning and related to the topic of the text.

Of course, there are no ready-made recipes and universal techniques suitable for all situations. But if the translator is prepared in advance for such problems, if he is aware of the essence, content, communicative function and stylistic effect of these and other features of the translated text, if he is able to recognize metaphors and allusions, irony and puns, etc., if he has the necessary background knowledge and understanding of the reality to which the text is devoted, there is a hope that its translation will be adequate enough. Of course, provided that the translator has the necessary professional skills and the relevant working languages.

English headlines are distinguished by their simple grammar. It is common practice to remove the verb "to be" in passive constructions:

Chinese traffic police given anti-smog nasal filters (27.03) instead of Chinese traffic police IS given anti-smog nasal filters;

French driver trapped for an hour in speeding 125mph car with no brakes (13.02) instead of French driver WAS trapped for an hour in speeding 125mph car with no brakes.

Articles and possessive pronouns are also omitted: *Princess Diana’s dress snapped up by anonymous bidder as surprise for wife.*

The Present Simple Tense is mainly used in headlines, even if past actions are described. The Present Simple tense gives a reader the feeling of simultaneity of events:

Paris fashion week: Raf Simons repeats Oscars triumph for Dior. (1.03)

Andrew Marr leaves hospital nearly two months after suffering a stroke. (01.03)

The use of quotations and direct speech is common for English headlines:

73-year-old bank robber 'wanted to return to jail'. (13.02)

Nicolas Sarkozy: I’d return to politics only to save France. (06.03)

Relaxation of US cannabis laws 'violates UN drug convention'. (22.03)

The jobseeker's story: 'I'm not proud to say I've gone begging'. (22.03)

Indirect speech is also occasionally used: *World's oldest person Jiroemon Kimura 115, says rise with the sun, read a paper. (07.03)*

Adoption reforms must slow down and give more support to parents, say peers. (06.03)

Foreign words and emotional lexics are often used:

French Communist party says adieu to the hammer and sickle (10.02) (adieu – french “Good bye”); Bonjour ... David Beckham introduces himself as a Paris Saint-Germain player. (31.01) (Bonjour – french “Good afternoon”).

Minami Minegishi of AKB48 appears in tearful mea culpa on YouTube after breaking her band's strict rules on dating, (mea culpa – (from Latin, often humorous, used when you are admitting that sth is your fault).

Readers can also come cross tropes in newspaper headlines:

Fashion renews its love affair with the royal family (metaphor). (22.03)

Newspaper articles frequently make use of cliches. One of the characteristics of newspaper style is this: on one hand, according to federal complaint, on the other, according to state media report, presumed, estimated, to be reported, it is claimed, it was proclaimed. On the other side,... refrained from commenting regarding the schedule, etc.

Infinitives like "to be expected," "to be said to," "to appear to," "to be likely to do," and "to fail to do" are also frequently used.

... and the proposal appears to have the support of David Cameron. (13.03)

But newspaper groups appeared to be moving to boycott the new system... (19.03)

The aid is expected to include civilian vehicle... (02.03)

The woman is said to have injured herself escaping from her first-floor room... (19.03)

Speaking about the translation of newspaper and magazine journalism, A. V. Fedorov makes the following generalization, which is quite applicable to the translation of informational texts:

-Conciseness of presentation, the desire to avoid unnecessary words.

-The use of already existing terminology in translation, without unnecessary, i.e., not given by the original, terms.

-The presence of figurative expressions that do not allow smoothing (preservation of the expressive features of the original, its tone), emotionally colored places (i.e., lively and bright colors).

-Clarity of syntax, especially when meeting long complex sentences, the translation of which is dangerous for ambiguity, confusion, etc. Hence the recommended use of breakdown (partitioning of sentences).

Conclusion

The results of the research show that the English newspaper article has the following features: lexical variety (from colloquial to scientific terms), the use of stylistic figures and tropes, which realize the influential function of newspaper texts. The syntax of the articles includes complex sentences, non-finite verb. All these features of newspaper article are determined by the striving for shortness, quick delivery of information as well as influential function.

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